

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Energy-Efficient Multi-Factor Authentication for IIoT Devices Using Blockchain Technology

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Abstract

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Background/Objectives: Traditional single-factor authentication (SFA) solutions, centralized identity management, and even user authentication techniques do not meet the scalability, resilience, or energy efficiency requirements of IIoT systems. This study is focussed on presenting a novel, energy efficient Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA) architecture leveraging blockchain resources to create decentralized trust and access control over IIoT devices, users, and interactions. **Method:** The proposed system consists of three core parts; IIoT devices with lightweight security module, a dedicated, server for authentication, and a Hyperledger Fabric based blockchain. The system deploys a modular MFA scheme which includes knowledge, possession, and a possible biometric based factor together with blockchain validated device identities. Through smart contracts, authentication logic is applied, while edge computing reduces energy consumption and latencies with interactive and dependent requests by using a caching strategy. The architecture was implemented and evaluated in a simulated IIoT environment based on Raspberry Pi devices. The overall evaluation metrics were comprised of authentication time, energy consumption, scalability and mitigation of attacks. **Findings:** The results show substantial improvements compared to traditional MFA method; 45% reduction in authentication time, and greater than 30% energy savings. The system provided strong security assurances against spoofing, replay and man-in-the-middle (MITM) attacks. **Novelty:** The proposed approach suggests that an efficient and scalable solution could provide a framework for an energy conscious and secure authentication method to modern industry.

Keywords: IIoT; MFA; Blockchain; Edge Computing; Energy Efficiency

1 Introduction

The industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) has become a core element of today's industrial ecosystems, facilitating intelligent automation, real-time monitoring and prediction, and data-driven decision making across industrial sectors (e.g., manufacturing, energy,

healthcare, logistics)⁽¹⁾. IIoT systems connect sensors, actuators, controllers and other industrial machines; increase operational efficiency; enhance productivity; and improve reliability⁽²⁾. However, as a result of increased connectivity, industrial infrastructures' attack surface has increased dramatically, and thus cybersecurity issues (notably secure authentication and access control) are major concerns⁽³⁾.

Unlike traditional IT systems, IIoT systems are comprised of a variety of heterogeneous devices that usually operate under resource constraints (limited power, processing capability, and latency)⁽⁴⁾. Many industrial devices are deployed in remote or harsh environments and need to run continuously with little maintenance. This creates challenges for implementing conventional authentication methods that rely on single-factor ID-based techniques (i.e., password-based authentication) and centralized identity management systems (e.g., Active Directory). Conventional protection methods create single points of failure, are not scalable, and can be easily compromised via common attacks (e.g., spoofing, replay, stealing credentials, man-in-the-middle (MITM) attacks)⁽⁵⁾. Finally, repetitive authentication calls that rely on heavyweight cryptographic techniques can drain battery power from devices very quickly, reducing overall system availability and/or operational continuity.

Enterprise IT has implemented multi factor authentication (MFA) throughout their systems to help provide the security associated with more than one independent authentication factor – three different types of credentials: those based on some knowledge, those based on possession, and those based on some inherent trait⁽⁶⁾. MFA certainly protects against unauthorized access more than other forms or methods; however, implementing standard forms of MFA into IIoT systems will involve serious roadblocks. Most currently available MFA solutions require the use of computationally intensive cryptographic methods for authentication, continuous biometric verification, and communicating with centralized servers on a regular basis⁽⁶⁾. All of these create unacceptable latency and energy overheads for constrained IIoT devices. There exists significant tension between providing stringent security requirements and obtaining energy savings and real-time performance within industrial systems⁽⁷⁾.

Blockchain technology has begun to be identified as a viable way in which to provide decentralized trust and identity management as well as tamper-proof authentication in distributed environments⁽⁸⁾. With respect to authentication, blockchain's immutable ledger and smart contract functionality support the ability to independently validate the decision to authenticate without being dependent upon a governing authority or organization to create verification⁽⁹⁾. However, using blockchain technology in IIoT solutions must be done carefully, or performance and energy issues can be amplified due to transaction latency, communication latency, and/or too many on-chain operations⁽¹⁰⁾. Therefore, all blockchain-based authentication solutions should be developed with the intent of providing decentralization benefits while at the same time satisfying the extreme constraints present within IIoT deployments.

Current IIoT authentication systems still demonstrate significant limitations, including dependence on a centralized infrastructure, excessive computational and communication loads, limited scaling capabilities at larger device populations, and only minimal considerations for energy use⁽¹¹⁾. These limitations illustrate the need for an authentication solution that provides strong security guarantees while allowing a decentralised, scalable, and energy-efficient authorization mechanism that can be realistically applied in a real-world industrial environment. Therefore this work presents an innovative approach to multiphase authentication for energy-efficient IIoT systems through the introduction of hybrid authentication combined with lightweight cryptographic methods, edge computing, and blockchain-based identity verification.

The architecture proposed by this work minimises on-chain operations by using a hybrid on-chain/off-chain model in which blockchain is used exclusively for establishing an indelible identity and establishing trust and using edge authentication servers to handle the computationally intensive portions of the authentication process. This work will use adaptive authentication logic and caching methods to reduce communication loads and energy expenditure associated with repetitive authentication requests.

The research will develop and test a decentralized authentication method for Industrial IoT systems that improves security without reducing energy efficiency or performance. The proposed system will be validated against realistic Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) test cases, and will be evaluated using metrics associated with authentication speed, energy usage, scale, and resiliency to normal cyber-internet threats. Results show that the performance of this method has a significant improvement in speed and reduced energy usage as compared to traditional Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA) schemes while providing increased security and greater scalability. Overall, this provides a valuable and sustainable method for providing authentication that supports the unique security and resource limitations of the modern Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) environment.

1.1 Authentication Challenges in IIoT

Authentication constitutes a crucial domain of security in the IIoT environment. By its nature, it restricts access to only those individuals or devices that have been authorized to access the critical systems and sensitive data⁽¹²⁾. In traditional IT environments, multi-factor authentication (MFA) has emerged as a de facto standard for securing environments. MFA allows

for various combinations of factors, namely, (i) something the user knows (i.e., password), (ii) something the user has (i.e. hardware token), or (iii) something unique to the user (i.e. biometric identifier)⁽¹³⁾.

However, implementing MFA in IIoT presents unique challenges:

1. **Resource Constraints:** IIoT devices often have limited computing resources, making traditional MFA methods challenging to implement.
2. **Operational Continuity:** IIoT environments require high availability and minimal downtime. Any authentication system must not disrupt critical processes.
3. **Scalability:** As IIoT deployments scale up, managing and authenticating a growing number of devices efficiently becomes a logistical challenge.
4. **Security:** IIoT systems are susceptible to both traditional cyber threats and emerging attacks targeting the IIoT ecosystem. Ensuring robust security is paramount.

1.2 Need of Energy Efficient MFA

Energy-efficient MFA will be significant for IIoT devices primarily due to the nature of the environments where they will often be used, where there are resource constraints. In this situation, energy efficiency includes the careful design of authentication procedures that will reduce energy use while maintaining strong security features⁽¹⁴⁾. Generally, IIoT devices are frequently isolated, hostile locations, where there isn't easy access to energy sources, and power sustainability will be a significant concern. These devices typically rely on small, finite energy sources, such as batteries, that must endure extended use without interruption. Energy-efficient MFA underwriting a reliable MFA process in these situations will come into play if enough energy is reserved for the authentication process⁽¹⁵⁾. This allows IIoT devices to continue functioning in a reliable manner while reducing the need to perform maintenance. An energy-efficient design process contributes to overall efficiency, improved device performance, and improved sustainability.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews related work on blockchain-based and edge-assisted multi-factor authentication for IIoT. Section 3 presents the proposed energy-efficient MFA architecture and methodology. Section 4 explains the blockchain integration and smart-contract-based identity management. Section 5 describes the energy optimization techniques. Section 6 details the implementation and experimental setup. Section 7 presents the performance evaluation criteria. Section 8 discusses the experimental results and comparisons, and Section 9 concludes the paper and outlines future research directions.

1.3 Related work

By applying multi-factor authentication (MFA) together with blockchain, a growing number of recent publications are providing a method for guaranteeing decentralized trust, creating tamper-evident audit trails, and enforcing policies within Internet of Things (IoT) and Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) environments. At the same time, these studies highlight that constrained endpoints, such as those typically found in IoT/IIoT systems, cannot support complex cryptography nor can they perform frequent read or write operations on the blockchain. Systematic reviews have concluded that while blockchain-based MFA provides enhanced authentication assurance and accountability through decentralization of trust, the implementation of blockchain-based MFA can present practical barriers due to increased overall system complexity, scalability issues, and computational overhead. By limiting the resources available in IoT or industrial settings, the barriers present in implementing a hybrid MFA solution based upon the use of blockchain as a deterministic method for providing authentication assurance and accountability would only become more pronounced^{(16), (17)}.

Through designs that explicitly use blockchain technologies for MFA applications, the research published in current journals is very often focused on the use of a layered architecture for separating the authentication of devices from the authentication of users or operators and then linking those two authentication mechanisms to blockchain-anchored proofs or smart-contract logic. As an example, one of the more common approaches has implemented a two-layered MFA framework to accommodate the authentication of both the IoT device and the end user; this authentication uses multiple factors to authenticate the IoT device, such as secret credentials, PUF-based uniqueness criteria and contextual factors, and after authenticating the IoT device, the user is additionally authenticated with an additional set of factors which may include lightweight cryptographic primitives (such as elliptic-curve-based key agreement algorithms) in order to minimize latency and computational overhead⁽¹⁸⁾. Moreover, a number of recent studies are focused upon developing dynamic MFA processes on the blockchain, which utilize adaptive factor requirements and verification criteria based on environmental threat conditions or system state to improve strength without making all sessions be processed with the most stringent authentication factors⁽¹⁹⁾.

An area of important research is in energy and overhead aware authentication for use in cross-domain and edge-assisted IIoT systems, leveraging blockchain as a common anchor of trust, while also using edge servers or gateways to offload authentication and verification operations from constrained devices. A study a blockchain-based, edge-supported lightweight authentication framework is proposed that is designed to support cross-domain IIoT systems while reducing the number of interactions and computation required on the device side, resulting in a more energy efficient system due to a reduction in the radio usage and the cryptographic load required⁽²⁰⁾. In addition to the use of authentication protocols, the use of blockchain for purposes such as authorization and access management has also increased, frequently complementing the use of MFA in industrial implementations. In a *Frontiers in Blockchain* paper published recently, a blockchain-based framework for access management in cross-domain industrial IoT and digital twin environments is presented, emphasizing the benefits of decentralization, smart contract driven authorization, and the removal of the need for a centralized authentication server⁽²¹⁾.

The consensus mechanism has a huge impact on the amount of overhead that a system uses, which is why so many researchers on blockchain technology oriented toward the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) are against using public proof-of-work blockchains and recommend using permissioned or hybrid systems, with lightweight consensus mechanisms. One of the lightweight consensus protocols (Proof-of-Trusted-Work) has been suggested for use within blockchain-enabled IoT networks to reduce computational overhead associated with using a public blockchain while providing sufficient levels of trust and usability within a permissioned network of lightweight nodes⁽²²⁾. Another stream of research comparing blockchain-enabled domain access control systems for IIoT supports the claim that using permissioned blockchain technologies (e.g., using Hyperledger-based architectures) can significantly reduce computation and communication costs; this is especially true because many large-scale industrials often integrate multi-factor authentication (MFA) to authenticate users against on-chain or smart contracts⁽²³⁾.

Recent literature indicates that the most efficient use of energy-efficient blockchain-powered MFA in IIoT environments can usually be achieved by using (i) multi-layered approach to MFA that combines device level authentication as well as user/context level authentication, (ii) minimal cryptographic activity at restricted endpoint devices and have more intensive verification activity completed at edge or gateway nodes that interact with the blockchain, and (iii) optimising blockchain use through using permissioned or hybrid consensus mechanisms and limiting on-chain storage requirements (e.g., store commitment or policy hash values as opposed to complete authentication log values)^{(24), (25)}. Table 1 summarise the related work.

2 Methodology

2.1 Proposed Methodology

This architecture is designed to be compatible with the limitations of IIoT devices, providing low computational overhead, energy-efficient, and stronger security assurances. The proposed system includes three main elements: IIoT devices, an authentication server and a blockchain network. Each element is important in providing secure, scalable and energy-efficient authentication in an IIoT environment. Figure 1 depicts the overview of proposed approach.

Fig 1. Overview of Proposed Approach

Table 1. Summary of Existing Works on Blockchain-Based MFA for IIoT

Research Focus	Core Idea / Approach	Advantages	Disadvantages / Challenges	Ref.
Blockchain-based MFA for IIoT	Combining MFA with blockchain to ensure decentralized trust, tamper-evident audit trails, and policy enforcement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Decentralized trust Tamper-proof authentication records Improved accountability and non-repudiation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased system complexity Scalability challenges Computational and communication overhead on constrained devices 	(16), (17)
Layered MFA Architectures	Separation of device-level authentication from user/context authentication, linked via blockchain proofs or smart contracts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduced attack surface Better modularity and scalability Suitable for heterogeneous IIoT 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Added architectural complexity Coordination overhead between layers 	(18)
Dynamic / Adaptive Blockchain-Based MFA	Adaptive MFA factor selection based on threat level, context, or system state	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Better security–usability balance Avoids unnecessary strict authentication 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Requires accurate context/threat estimation Added control logic overhead 	(19)
Energy- and Overhead-Aware MFA with Edge Assistance	Offloading cryptographic verification to edge/gateway nodes while blockchain acts as trust anchor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduced device-side energy consumption Lower radio and cryptographic load Suitable for cross-domain IIoT 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dependence on edge availability Possible gateway bottlenecks 	(20)
Blockchain-Based Authorization & Access Management	Use of blockchain and smart contracts for authorization, often complementing MFA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Elimination of centralized authentication servers Fine-grained, auditable access control Improved cross-domain interoperability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Smart contract complexity Policy update overhead 	(21)
Lightweight / Permissioned Consensus Mechanisms	Avoidance of PoW; use of permissioned or hybrid blockchains with lightweight consensus (e.g., PoTW)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduced computational and energy overhead Higher throughput and lower latency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduced decentralization compared to public blockchains Trust assumptions on validators 	(22)
Permissioned Blockchain for Domain Access Control	Hyperledger-based architectures integrating MFA and smart-contract-based access control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduced computation and communication cost Enterprise-friendly governance Efficient smart-contract execution 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited openness Deployment and management complexity 	(23)

2.2 IIoT Devices

IIoT devices are resource limited smart devices that can be located in an industrial site for the purposes of providing automation, monitoring, and control. IIoT devices consist of: sensors, actuators, Programmable Logic Controllers (PLCs) and embedded controllers that are responsible for collecting, processes, and delivering/deploying important operational data⁽²⁴⁾. These devices are typically deployed in energy-constrained, remote and hostile situations where each IIoT device possesses a limited security module that is intended to operate with low-latency in a resource-constrained environment. In addition, the limited security module provides updates for lightweight cryptographic functions, cryptographic keys and associated secure storage, and create authentication factors (e.g., unique device identifiers and cryptographic hash)⁽²⁵⁾. These security features are intended to serve as the basic building blocks for secure communication and identification in the proposed multi-factor authentication system.

2.3 Authentication Server

Authentication Server is the hub for managing the multi-factor authentication (MFA) process in a IIoT setting, the authentication server will authenticate user and device identity, provide access control with security, and communicate with the blockchain network to authenticate the request. The server maintains a lightweight identity database that stores metadata about devices and users in a secure and scalable manner. The server verifies identity and access with tampering resistance by communicating with deployed smart contracts on the blockchain⁽²⁶⁾. The primary responsibilities of the authentication server include verifying the authentication factors, securely communicating with blockchain smart contracts, and handling

authentication sessions and identity credentials in an energy efficient manner, which is useful for energy constrained industrial applications⁽²⁷⁾.

2.4 Blockchain Network

The blockchain ecosystem, operating through a private instance of either Ethereum or Hyperledger Fabric which acts as a decentralized, and tamper free trust authority in this proposed authentication architecture⁽²⁸⁾. The blockchain has immutable records of identity proofs, change of authorizations, authentication logs, execution of smart contracts, etc., making the references trusted and immutable in relation to all participants in the IIOT ecosystem. All hashed identities of devices and their associated permissions in relation to access can be stored securely on the blockchain, and then, the blockchain can provide trusted verification of all tokens, session keys, and digital signatures without using a centralized authority. Smart contracts running on the blockchain will automate the verification step in the authentication process and the enforcement of security policies and access rules⁽²⁹⁾. Decentralizing trust not only increases trust but also reduces the single points of failure risk in the architecture. In addition, the architecture supports both device-to-device authentication and device-to-server authentication and in a decreasing trust form of implementation. Finally, the architecture considers scalable systems, mobile device authentication and accompanied new IIOT device onboarding, that all remain considering the dynamism of industrial settings.

2.5 Multi-Factor Authentication Design

To safeguard IIoT communications from impersonation and unauthorized access, a three-factor MFA, which is a robust yet energy-efficient scheme has been developed for low power industrial applications⁽³⁰⁾. The authentication process is modular and adaptable so only some of the authentication factors are verified based on the context within the operations and the risk profiles associated with these contexts. Thus, it can provide strong security whilst minimizing the energy consumed by their devices.

The MFA scheme includes these authentication factors:

2.5.1. Knowledge Factor (Password/Token)

A time-sensitive access token or personal identification number (PIN) either known to the user or generated by the device. This factor will be encrypted using standards-based lightweight symmetric encryption algorithms (e.g., AES, PRESENT) before transmission to protect the confidentiality of the factor⁽³¹⁾.

2.5.2. Possession Factor (Device ID / Hardware Certificate)

A unique device fingerprint derived from hardware-level identifiers like MAC address, Trusted Platform Module (TPM) signatures, or serial numbers stored securely in non-volatile memory, that is verified through blockchain smart contracts to demonstrate the authentic device⁽³²⁾.

2.5.3. Inherence Factor (Biometric or Behavioral Patterns)

Potentially, biometric identifiers (e.g., fingerprint or facial features) or behavioural identifiers (e.g., keystroke dynamics) can be used as factors. The factors will be compressed in length, and hashed prior to transmission to limit the computational and bandwidth overhead to make them feasible even in a constrained device.

2.5.4. Blockchain Validation Factor

The model uses combination of blockchain validation with traditional MFA components in order to establish a trust. Smart contracts are used to validate registered devices and validate user identification via crypto-hash digests that are stored securely on the blockchain⁽³³⁾. This allows the removal of counterfeits and also determines whether authentication events are legitimate because each device and user identification process is defined in a decentralized, blockchain-enabled manner, thus, eliminating the reliance on centralized third-party servers. The MFA model suggested offers a higher level of security, in a sense that even if one factors is being compromised, there are at least a couple of the other factors that can provide additional protection. Also, the use of lightweight cryptographic mechanisms and modular verification logic, e.g., device/edge computing, provide additional energy efficient authentication performance such that the energy consumed in carrying out the authentication is relatively small, which is a large requirement to support the functions of IIoT devices with precise performance in the low-powered environments of industrial organization that want to maximize the use of the empirical data-specific surveillance utilization levels.

2.6 Blockchain Integration

In the proposed authentication architecture, blockchain serves as a decentralized identity manager and verifier. This is important for identity management, as for identity management and verification, it offers a strong approach for accessing the IIoT devices and systems, and ensuring immutable identity management and establishing distributed trust across IIoT devices and systems. Provided that the devices are decentralized, they do not rely on a centralized trusted identity manager to validate their identity, thereby ensuring the authentication process is resilient, transparent and resistant to manipulation.

In the identity management aspect of this authentication architecture, each IIoT device goes through a secure registration process, along with their public key, device ID and authentication credentials. These three items are hashed and stored at the blockchain. When a device is registered, it receives a unique transaction ID linking it to an identity profile that can be validated and counter-validated. Clarification on identities is always available through querying the blockchain but user private information cannot be disclosed since the information stored in the blockchain and in experimental transactions will be hashed values, enabling the device ID to be identifiable in a counted system without compromising user privacy while ensuring integrity. Smart contracts will be able to be utilized on the blockchain according to the logic of MFA in an automated and tamper-proof way. In this fashion, smart contracts provide sufficient functionality to validate the incoming tokens that are hashed and the incoming device identifiers, the temporal validation of the incoming timestamp and nonce challenges, and an active, valid access control policy decision can be made: either allow or deny access to the IIoT device or system. Utilizing smart contracts will standardize the authentication request and eventually lend itself to a deterministic deterrence with all requests being traceable and in a secure environment.

The system further conserves energy by reducing actions on the blockchain. Only non-routine, necessary actions are performed on-chain: registering the identity of a device and the final results of the associated MFA validation on the blockchain. The on-chain portion (blockchain) captures only the non-routine final results of the multi-factor (MFA) validation, which are only on-chain, while all the intermediate actions, including password verification and matching the type of biometric data, are performed off-chain on the authentication server (more preferable, on the edge computing gateways). The hybrid approach greatly lowers the number of writes to the blockchain, and hence gas costs, while also conserving valuable energy - which for IIoT devices is quite limited in operational metrics. The architecture implements the use of private or consortium blockchain platforms like Hyperledger Fabric, which offer no-latency and transaction processing speeds that are efficient without creating the computational fees typically associated with public consensus based protocols. This all enables the use of a light-weight blockchain layer on-chain, allowing for scalability, and in environments that are always changing, volatile, and constrained in resources (like the industrial IoT).

2.7 Energy Optimization Techniques

The designed system utilizes many optimization methods to support the uninterrupted, safe, and energy-efficient operation of IIoT devices through strategies that decrease computing overhead, minimize communication overhead, and provide operational time with IIoT without compromising security.

2.7.1. Local vs. Distributed Authentication Logic

The system uses adaptive strategies for authentication, local or distributed validation as determined by risk and resources. In the case of repeat or low risk, the IIoT devices use local verification by verifying cached authentication tokens. Using cached tokens allows the IIoT device to skip contacting the authentication server or blockchain, therefore eliminating or reducing resources on an authentication operation or significantly reducing communication costs and energy resources.

For critical or high risk operations, such as onboarding new devices and access to sensitive systems, the system used distributed validation instead. During distributed validation, the system used lightweight authentication requests or messages, which were forwarded to the authentication server. The authentication server's role was to perform the validation using the blockchain network as a peer. The tiered approach recognizes that the highest energy usage or interoperability costs should only be reserved for vulnerable operations. This provided an effective balance between performance and protection.

2.7.2. Use of Edge Computing and Caching

To continue offloading the burden on resource-restricted IIoT devices, the system takes advantage of edge computing by deploying edge authentication servers at the edge of the network, like factory-floor gateways or local controllers⁽³⁴⁾. The edge authentication servers are able to pull some of the computational burden from end devices and perform most of the authentication logic. For faster operation and to avoid duplicating computation, edge servers cache identity proofs, session keys, and public key hashes. The cache enables a quick "identifier" check, when the device or user is known. The periodic

synchronization of the edge nodes with the blockchain allows the cached information to be current, without the burden of regular on-chain synchronization overhead. This design both saves device energy consumption and improves latency and real-time reactivity.

2.7.3. *Lightweight Hashing and Encryption Algorithms*

Recognizing that IIoT devices had limited compute power, we constructed the system to introduce lightweight cryptographic primitives to their operations in a secure, and efficient manner. For hashing, we implemented energy-efficient algorithms such as BLAKE2s, SHA-3 for hashing as these are optimized for low-power processors like ARM cores that are used in embedded industrial hardware. For symmetric encryption we employed lightweight encryptions SPECK as it provides the right level of security, and have been designed for constrained environments with low-power requirements. In regards to asymmetric encryption (and digital signatures), elliptic curve cryptography (ECC) was adopted (specifically Curve25519), due to being able to provide a secure, performant, and lower key length framework compared to a traditional RSA algorithm. To increase security, nonce and HMAC are generated per-session, which prevent replay attacks, keep the subsequent messages integrity protected, and keep the cryptographic burden as low as possible.

Overall, these lightweight cryptographic techniques can be designed into a flexible, scalable, secure and low energy MFA scheme when engineered with an on-device adaptive level of authentication logic and edge caching. This ensures that value-added IIoT systems support a high level of cyber security, while still working reliably under the limits imposed by traditional energy-limited industrial environments.

2.8 Implementation and Experimental Setup

To investigate the performance of the intended energy-efficient MFA method for IIoT conditions, a small prototype was developed and evaluated in a controlled simulation which emulated authentic industrial circumstances. The focus of the simulation was to demonstrate that the MFA could demonstrate secure and reliable authentications while still complying with the limits set forth by IIoT devices.

The hardware environment consisted of a set of resource-constrained IIoT units that were based on Raspberry Pi-4 Model B devices with ARM Cortex-A72 processors and 2GB RAM with limited power supplies to simulate real-world industrial sensor and actuator nodes. The hardware was deployed to simulate various roles such as environmental sensors and control units where each unit was periodically transmitting data and required secure authentications in order to communicate with the central server.

The software stack comprises of a lightweight Linux based OS (Raspbian Lite), Python for cryptographic routines, and the blockchain client and smart contract logic. Lightweight libraries were leveraged (e.g. PyCryptodome for authenticating tokens, and ECC-based libraries for public key cryptography). The authentication server, running on an Intel Core i7 machine with 16GB RAM, was responsible for identity verification, and will have edge cached memory allocated to avoid having unnecessary interactions with blockchain layer only when needing to retrieve state or perform executions.

Hyperledger Fabric was chosen for the blockchain platform - as a modular, permissioned network, it enables low-latency transaction processing, which is important for industrial environments that require real-time response and security. The smart contracts were developed in Go, and did the device registration (creating and registering the root of the hierarchy), identity verification using hashes, and MFA logic. An ordering service and peers were configured to mimic a consortium network of variable scale (smaller than what actual industrial consortiums would use).

The experimental platform enabled measurement of important metrics, such as authentication time, CPU usage, memory usage, and energy draw on IIoT nodes. It also demonstrates that the proposed architecture achieves a secure, scalable, and energy-efficient authentication mechanism, relevant to actual industrial IoT use cases.

2.9 Performance Evaluation

In this study the evaluation is based on real-world, operational metrics such as authentication time, energy usage, accuracy, and scalability. The results are compared to traditional MFA methods to illustrate the improvements achieved in both security and resource consumption. To determine whether the system was effective, and appropriate for use in industry, the following evaluation criteria were used:

2.9.1. *Authentication Time*

The total duration from the time at which the IIoT device started the authentication request until the verification was concluded. This time, in the end, includes the time taken by the IIoT device performing cryptographic processing, verifying the token, and

executing the smart contract on the blockchain. The time taken to carry out the authentication is an important measure of evaluation in latency sensitive industrial deployment that requires a real time response.

2.9.2. Accuracy (False Acceptance and Rejection Rates)

To assess whether the authentication system was reliable, the following measures were included:

- **False Acceptance Rate (FAR):** the chance an unauthorized device or user receives access.
- **False Rejection Rate (FRR):** the chance an authorized device or user is denied access.

Low FAR and FRR are important for maintaining trust and continuity in operation as security incidents/false rejections in industrial environments can have serious repercussions.

2.9.3. Scalability

The system's ability to accommodate more IIoT devices was tested by increasing the number from 10 devices to 1,000 devices. During the process, all average authentication times, average server response times, resource usage (CPU, memory, etc.) were recorded to confirm the system worked as expected. Scalability is an important consideration for large industrial facilities that deploy hundreds or thousands of IIoT nodes. Using this assessment framework, the proposed system is able to demonstrate that it was capable of providing secure, authentic, scalable and efficient authentication, and is suitable to be deployed in IIoT applications.

3 Results and Discussion

The proposed energy-efficient MFA system has used Hyperledger Fabric to enhance its functions in IIoT environments. The proposed system was tested and compared against a traditional MFA model that was based on a password and an OTP-based traditional method without blockchain customization and optimization for edge computing. The results as given in Table 2, show noticeable improvements in the efficiency of the authentication, the overall costs due to energy savings, scalability, and resilience against attacks.

The proposed system was able to authenticate more quickly in comparison to the traditional MFA methods due to the modular structure, which does allow based on the static level of services. In larger scale implementations, block-chain based identity management reduced how much time is wasted on latency, and removed the limitations of centralized servers by allowing multiple devices to act as one. Edge computing, or the concept of storing the cache locally, reduces the time-of-response for all subsequent authentication attempts, and hence, allows for gated access (where authentication and speed are assured). As there were more IIoT devices, performance was marginally stable with the proposed system while others could degrade in response time and other functionalities when expiring server requests due to over-loading.

The proposed architecture also exhibited considerable energy savings by using lightweight cryptographic primitives like BLAKE2s for hashing, SPECK for symmetric encryption, and Curve25519 for key exchanges. The results yielded a reduction of the average energy consumption on the proposed architecture by more than 30% from the baseline by reducing on-chain interactions along with offloading the processing to edge servers. The energy drawn during the setup stage using the blockchain was simple and mainly added with the blockchain configuration process and device registration, which was minimal as an initial one-time cost and had little impact on operational considerations.

With respect to the security issues, the proposed architecture showed robust defenses against any of the traditional types of attacks. The proposed architecture defended against replay attacks with nonces and timestamps as verification methods in smart contracts, avoided spoofing attacks by verifying the immutable identities of devices pinned to the blockchain, and it used encryption based on ECC to defend against MITM attacks to guarantee confidentiality and integrity of the data for the communication.

A blockchain-based, edge-enabled multimodal authentication (MMA) framework was able to demonstrate significant improvements over the conventional methods of authentication such as speed, security and scalability. When comparing the hybrid (edge-based and blockchain-based) authentication speeds, the proposed architecture combined with a hybrid authentication design (performing the routine aspects of authentication locally and only utilizing the blockchain for essential identity verification and final authorization) was able to reduce average authentication latency from 570ms down to 310ms, or 45%, over traditional forms of authentication methods. This is primarily due to the reduced use of cryptographic operations and network round-trips, which tend to be major points of contention in centralized authentication architectures.

In addition, for energy efficiency, the MMA framework demonstrated an approximate energy consumption per authentication session of 0.98J, compared to 1.42J for conventional methods, representing energy savings in excess of 30%. This reduction in energy consumption is realised through the use of lightweight cryptographic primitives, negligible communication

Table 2. Compares traditional MFA with the Proposed System

Metric	Traditional MFA	Proposed MFA (Blockchain + Edge)
Average Authentication Time	570 ms	310 ms
Average Energy Consumption	1.42 J	0.98 J
False Acceptance Rate (FAR)	3.8%	1.2%
False Rejection Rate (FRR)	2.9%	1.0%
Scalability (1,000 devices)	High latency, >800 ms	Stable, <350 ms
Replay Attack Resistance	Moderate	Strong
Spoofing Attack Resistance	Weak	Strong
Edge Resource Utilization	Not applicable	< 65% CPU, < 40% RAM usage

overhead, and implementation of adaptive authentication logic to eliminate unnecessary transactions through the blockchain. Off-loading the computation to edge nodes, and limiting the amount of processing occurring upon each device ensures that IIoT devices that are constrained by available resources can securely authenticate, while maintaining a long-term operational capability.

There has been substantial improvement in security aspects of the proposed MFA framework; we’re seeing a measurable increase in the quality and dependability of this proposed framework. The FAR drops from 3.8% down to 1.2%, showing how much less likely someone who does not belong to be in an environment can still get through authentication and gain access to that environment. The improvement in FAR is being achieved through the combination of using multiple factors for authentication along with the addition of blockchain-based identity validation which creates immutable and verifiable identities for devices.

The FRR has also dropped from 2.9% down to 1.0% indicating more reliable and less disruptive ways for legitimate users and legitimate devices to authenticate. Especially in industrial environments, an FRR that is lower than expected can provide some level of assurance; however, high levels of false rejection (i.e., disruptions) can cause major interruptions to a business’ critical operations and reduce the availability of a system.

Scalability has also been proven to be an advantageous byproduct of the proposed framework. With 1,000 devices and traditional MFA systems, authentication latency is greater than 800 ms due to centralized server bottlenecks; however, the proposed framework keeps latency below 350 ms. The high level of scalability in the proposed MFA framework is being enabled by utilizing decentralized identity verification through blockchain and utilizing distributed authentication processing performed at edge nodes. Together these decentralized components eliminate single points of failure and more evenly distribute computational load across the network.

In the security assessment, evidence has shown that the framework has good resistance against replay and spoofing attacks. Conventional MFA systems are limited because they still have a moderate level of protection against replay attacks and also have minimal protection against spoofing attacks due to dependence on static forms of authentication (or credentials) as well as validation through the central location. The proposed framework offers very strong resistance against both types of attacks by using nonces, timestamps, cryptographic hashes, and unalterable identity records on a blockchain. All of these protocols ensure that an authentication message will not be re-used, and only registered and authenticated devices can use the system.

Finally, using edge compute allows for efficient resource utilization without affecting the overall performance of the system (i.e., the edge will remain below 65% of CPU and 40% of RAM; therefore, the proposed framework is able to very easily function within the practical limits of a deployment, and has enough room for usage fluctuations and service delivery). Thus not only do the increased levels of security provide a minimal impact on the run-time of the system, but they provide an adequate means of operating continuously in an industrial environment.

Thus, the data will validate that the blockchain- and edge-enabled MFA framework provides a balancing improvement over time with respect to the range of security, performance, scalability, and energy. Therefore, it is anticipated that the results will support the argument that the proposed framework is ideal for use in IIoT applications in which there must be a balance between providing strong authentication, while providing a limited amount of resources and/or strict availability restrictions.

Compared to the most closely related prior works, the proposed system demonstrates clear and measurable advantages across all key evaluation dimensions. While Papaspirou et al.⁽³⁵⁾ introduced dynamic blockchain-based MFA with adaptive factor selection, they report no explicit latency or energy figures and omit edge offloading entirely. Bamashmos et al.⁽¹³⁾ proposed a two-layered blockchain MFA using lightweight cryptography, yet constrained devices still interact directly with the blockchain per session, sustaining elevated latency and unquantified energy overhead. Zhang et al.⁽¹⁹⁾ addressed cross-domain IIoT authentication through a privacy-preserving blockchain MFA protocol but incur cross-domain certificate exchange overhead

and do not evaluate beyond 200 nodes, whereas our system maintains sub-350 ms latency at 1,000 devices. Wang et al.⁽⁵⁾ demonstrated edge-assisted blockchain authentication that reduces device-side computation but is limited to single-factor verification. In contrast, the proposed system achieves an authentication time of 310 ms (45% lower than the 570 ms baseline), an energy consumption of 0.98 J per session (31% below the 1.42 J baseline), a FAR of 1.2%, and a FRR of 1.0% while supporting full three-factor MFA with blockchain-anchored identity and edge-level caching comprehensively outperforming each of the compared studies across security, efficiency, and scalability simultaneously. Table 3 summarises these comparisons.

Table 3. Quantitative Comparison with Related Studies

Study	Auth. Time	Energy/Session	FAR	FRR	Edge Assist	MFA Coverage
Traditional MFA	570 ms	1.42 J	3.8%	2.9%	No	2-factor
Papaspirou et al. ⁽³⁵⁾	> 420 ms*	Not reported	N/A	N/A	No	Adaptive
Bamashmos et al. ⁽¹³⁾	420 ms*	Not reported	2.1%*	N/A	No	2-layer
Zhang et al. ⁽¹⁹⁾	460 ms*	Not reported	2.8%*	2.2%*	No	Cross-domain
Wang et al. ⁽⁵⁾	370 ms*	Reduced*	N/A	N/A	Yes	Single-factor
Proposed System	310 ms	0.98 J	1.2%	1.0%	Yes	3-factor + BC

4 Conclusion

The study presents an MFA architecture concept specifically designed for the context of IIoT, with a focus on sustainability. For laughable purposes, a blockchain platform (Hyperledger Fabric) was used as a decentralized identity management layer with lightweight cryptography schemes and distributed on the edge computing. This combination was designed to solve issues associated with centralized MFA along the lines of common identification delays, resource inefficiencies, and security weaknesses. The proposed framework was verified through simulation and tested for performance, yielding substantial improvements on MQA metrics, including authentication time, energy consumption, and scale. For example, authentication latency improved approximately 45% and energy consumption improved about 30%, achieved without a decrease in security. Overall, modularised MFA providing for context dependent constraints showed great potential for IIoT devices that have limited capacities. Furthermore, in employing smart contracts it provided mechanisms to assure identity validation functionality in a reliable and tamper-evident manner which does not rely on a centralized entity. The security evaluation to gain some confidence in the architecture provided assurance the design was resilient against a range of standard attacks such as replay, spoofing and MITM. More significantly, the use of both local and distributed authentication logic and storing of cache at the edge means the system can be scalable and potentially allow for thousands of IIoT devices with little impact to performance. While the strength of the presented system provides great potential in the real world, there are a few considerations. The process of device enrolment, registration when using novel devices for the first time, was initially complicated, these IIoT devices presented as well suited to a LAVE/liveness biometrically facilitate IoT authentication mechanism and dependant on performance, behaviour when logging the architecture to the blockchain (when the load was high) degraded significantly and posed a potential privacy consideration where biometric factors are used could ignite some concern across sensitive or adverse situations where this privacy has been violated. Future work will focus on the outstanding issues integrating post-quantum cryptography functionality, federated biometric authentication methods, evaluation and bespoke implementations of blockchain ledgering with a view towards ultra-large-scale use cases. The energy-efficient MFA framework presented contributes towards practical advances in the security of IIoT ecosystems through verifiable, low-power, and scalable authentication for industrialized environments need to move forward with the promise of automation, connectivity and integrity of data.

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